

LEXICO-SEMANTIC FIELD OF MENTAL STATES AND ITS COGNITIVE CLASSIFIERS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE.

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of lexico-semantic field of mental states and its cognitive classifiers in the English language. Moreover, semantic mental state names in English were analyzed on the base of the word "knowledge".

A characteristic feature of modern language science is the formation and development of cognitive linguistics as a new scientific paradigm, in which language is studied as a cognitive mechanism.

The study of human mental activity, the correlation of knowledge structures that make up concepts - operational units of memory, the mental lexicon and natural language, the search for classification categories that structure mental constructs and their reflection in the language, leads researchers to an understanding of cognitive classifiers - actual classification features, "ordering both reality and language for a person".

The study of language and thinking shows that the basis of knowledge about the world is such a unit of mental information as a concept. E.S. Kubryakova defines the concept as an operational, meaningful unit of thinking, a unit or quantum of structured knowledge.

Since the reflection of the world in the human mind is carried out through concepts that are different in their content, organization and method of representation, different types of concepts are distinguished: representations (mental pictures), schemes, concepts, frames, scenarios (scripts), gestalts. According to the degree of stability, concepts are divided into stable and unstable. According to the form of expression, concepts can be verbalized and hidden. According to the degree of abstractness, abstract and concrete concepts are distinguished. According to the way of representation in the language, lexical, phraseological, syntactic concepts are considered. The discussion of the term concept, the development of types of concepts and grounds for their classification continues.

The vocabulary of a language is a system, the individual links of which is naturally interconnected and constantly interacts. The study of the lexico-semantic

system of the language involves the consistent selection and study of its individual elements and, accordingly, the relationship between them.

Many researchers agree that the main constitutive unit of the lexico-semantic system of a language is the word in its semantic relations and lexical connections at the level of its individual meaning - the lexico-semantic version of the word.

The lexico-semantic version of a word includes two components: a lexeme and a sememe. A lexeme is a unit of the expression plan, a sequence of phonemes that makes up the sound range of a word. A sememe is a unit of the content plan, a mental image associated with a given lexeme, evoked by it in the mind.

The denotative second sememe (D2) (derived-nominative meaning according to V.V. Vinogradov) reflects some essence of the phenomenon of reality through its comparison with the D1 sememe. The name of the D1 sememe is transferred to the D2 sememe.

Other semes are connotative. They contain a variety of additional meanings that express feelings, desires, assessments, aesthetic empathy and other impressions of the denotation. Connotative sememes differ in the type of connection with denotative sememes of the same lexeme. The connotative first sememe (K1) is in a logically motivated connection with its denotative sememe. It reflects some essence through the image of a denotative sememe, which is denoted by their common lexeme, and is expressed only in phrases.

Combinations of lexemes, in which the types of their sememes are manifested, Z.D. Popova calls phrase combinations

(Popova, 1993, p.31). In phrase combinations, one more type of sememe is found: connotative isolated (KZ). Such a sememe is carried by a lexeme that does not have denotative sememes. The KZ sememe is actualized only as part of idioms. M.M.Kopylenko, Z.D.Popova distinguish the following types of two-lexical phrase combinations:

1) D1D1 phrase combinations are free, their meaning is equal to the sum of the values of the combined semes;

2) phrase combinations D1D2, D2D2, D1K1, D2K1, D1K2, D2K2, D1KZ, D2KZ are called stable or phrase combinations, among them there are many terms, compound names;

3) phrase combinations K1K1 are called phraseological units or phraseological units;

4) phrase combinations K1K2, K2K2, K1KZ, K2KZ are called idioms or phraseological fusions.

V.M.Toporova details the classification of sememe types developed in the concept of M.M.Kopylenko and Z.D.Popova. Sememes of the same status (D1, D2, K1) can differ in the degree of abstractness / concreteness of the representation of the object of thought. V.M. Toporova distinguishes the following semes: "concrete post-abstract", "concrete geomegrized", "abstract theoretical", "abstract symbolic", "generalized-empirical". The abstract-concrete antinomy is one of the main ones in philosophy and logic - "is one of the difficult to comprehend, interpreted, and therefore ambiguous", the concept of abstraction is difficult to explain.

The dialectics of the abstract and the concrete predetermines the difficulty of delimiting the concrete and the abstract

word. In linguistics, there is no single criterion for opposing an abstract and a concrete name. The most famous is the interpretation of the abstract as conceptual, mental, as opposed to the concrete as sensual, visual. According to the Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary: "From the point of view of the content plan, abstract words are distinguished in the vocabulary, i.e. words with a generalized meaning, and specific words, i.e. words with subjective, "real" meaning", "the semantics of nominations, embodied in the form of specific nouns, reflects the substantial, sensually perceptible image of the designated.

As we abstract from the substantial properties, the degree abstractness...". In many linguistic works, the incorrectness of opposing the abstract and the concrete only as "sensory" and "conceptual" is noted, since linguistic semantics is characterized by a close connection between the sensible and the rational.

The complexity of comprehending the dichotomy abstract - concrete determines the plurality of definitions of the abstract name. Yu.S. Stepanov contrasts abstract names as non-referential, non-denotative vocabulary with denotative vocabulary, tending to designate concepts, significations.

N.V. Ufimtseva refers names with a denotative and denotative-significative meaning to a specific vocabulary, and words with a significative and significative-denotative basis of meaning to an abstract one. An interesting approach is N.D. Arutyunova, who, based on the syntactic possibilities of the name (in particular, the degree of its syntactic freedom), divides substantives into three classes: names of a person / non-person, names of a concrete-

objective and abstract-event meaning. N.D. Arutyunova comes to the conclusion that "the more objective the meaning of a noun, the more difficult it is for it to be directly included in the system of sentence forms".

The search for ways to define an abstract name continues in line with the study of the criteria for highlighting abstract vocabulary and its differences from concrete vocabulary. Many works are devoted to the material connotations of an abstract name and the role of metaphor in the representation of abstract entities.

In recent linguistic works, issues "related to the analysis of an abstract name from cognitive positions" are considered. L.O. Cherneiko in his work "Linguistic and philosophical analysis of an abstract name" postulates that the content of an abstract name is a concept that includes logical and sublogical strata. In terms of structure, the concept is represented by gestalts and images. L.O. Cherneiko proposes a method for analyzing the compatibility of abstract names, which makes it possible to model the gestalt structure of the concept behind it. L.O. Cherneiko identifies a number of features of abstract concepts. Native speakers master abstract nominations unconsciously, due to their involvement in a certain language community, therefore abstract concepts are "transpersonal", as they have been developed by mankind over many millennia.

In lexicographic practice, there are various definitions of abstract concepts. Explanatory dictionaries "record the most common features of abstract names, taking their subjective figurative-sensual specificity beyond the scope." The essence of abstract concepts is "subjective in nature", rarely has the same content for different people, that is, their invariant

content is much less than the variable part that depends on individual personal experience.

Abstract concepts are revealed in the form of the same cognitive structures as specific concepts: scenarios, frames, schemes, mental pictures, and so on, which are capable of changing "kaleidoscopically", which is explained by the specifics of the multidimensional mental object behind the abstract name. In this regard, in foreign linguistics, an abstract concept is often described in terms of a "concept with fuzzy boundaries" - a construct with a fuzzy scope and content.

A large number of modern linguistic works are devoted to understanding the features of abstract concepts. Many abstract concepts are analyzed in collections on the logical analysis of language. The concepts of the intellectual and emotional sphere are considered. The subject of intensive cognitive research is the concepts of the sphere of human characteristics, actions and relationships. Linguists are interested in concepts that reflect signs of reality and groups of interconnected abstract concepts. Studies are being carried out on the features of perception of abstract concepts, analysis of abstract nominations by means of a psycholinguistic experiment. These studies provide extensive material for understanding the ways of organizing abstract knowledge in the human mind and its representation in language.

Revealing the content of abstract concepts, features of their structuring and classifiers that determine their essence requires careful study and is an urgent task of cognitive linguistic research. According to the typology of semes according to D\K,

the semantheme of the KNOWLEDGE lexeme includes the following semes:

1. Sememe D1 ...state of understanding; ...the state of being aware of something or possessing information [Webster, 1961,1373]. (...the state of understanding...the state of being aware of something or having information). Sememe D1 is fixed in the phrases: inside (internal), intimate (intimate), intuitive (intuitive), sensitive (sensual), abstractive (abstract, abstract), representative (characteristic), intellective (intellectual) knowledge [Webster, 1961, 1373] , to be common knowledge (a lot of people know about it, although that person would prefer to keep it a secret) [Longman , 1993,734], etc.

A disagreement flared up between the two directors and this soon became common knowledge throughout the firm. [Longman, 1993,734] (became known throughout the firm). Not answered with the soothing remarks only to be expected from somebody who had no knowledge of this part of her life. [BE,B2G 251] (no knowledge of this side of her life).

It represents an instinctive knowledge acquired by trial and error of how to maintain an inner balance... [BE, HY6 192] (instinctive knowledge). Sarella quivered with the knowledge that for sure he wanted something again. [BE, JXU 4134] (trembled at the knowledge that he definitely wanted something again).

... but the simple knowledge that there was now one person in the small, enclosed community who cared for him healed Richard's wounded spirit. [BE, APU 2065] (the mere knowledge that there was not a single person in the small, closed community who cared about him). Calmed a little, he too walked off, in the opposite direction, safe in the knowledge that no

one in their right mind, regardless of politics, would dare to stand in his way. [BE, FRS 36] (feeling safe in the knowledge that no one in their right mind... would dare to stand in his way). But it was a magical time because running through everything like a fine, golden thread was the knowledge that we loved one another. [BE, HOF 2935] (the knowledge that we loved each other).

2. Sememe D21 Familiarity gained by actual experience; practical skills; technical acquaintance [Webster, 1961, 1373]. (Knowledge acquired through experience; practical skills; technical skills).

My knowledge of Japanese is limited to a few phrases. [Longman,1993,734] (knowledge of Japanese)

His interest in, and knowledge of inner-city problems is more profound and personally felt than that of most government ministers and civil servants, according to those who have spent time with him. [BE, ADB 243] (knowledge of inner city problems).

Benny thought, trying to recall her knowledge of this period of history. [BE, FSR 689] (knowledge of this period of history).

The D21 sememe determines the type of knowledge object: knowledge of surgery (surgery), literature (literature), tools and simple machines (tools and simple mechanisms), knowledge in design (in design), industry (in industry), knowledge concerning the phenomenon of (knowledge concerning the phenomenon) [BE], etc.

Sememe D21 is realized in phrases with adjectives denoting varieties of existing knowledge: psychological (psychological), technical (technical)

speaking (ability to speak), reading (ability to read) [CD, 1990,139, Webster, 1961,1373], firsthand knowledge (knowledge gained through personal experience) (to know from personal experience, to experience for yourself (knowledge gained through personal experience) [Longman, 1993,734], astronomical (astronomical), metrological (metrological), applied (applied), practical (practical) knowledge [BE], etc.

Sememe D21 is updated in phrases that give a qualitative assessment of the content of existing knowledge: profound (deep), thorough (complete), rudimentary (elementary), slight (insignificant), superficial (superficial) [CD,1990,139], sufficient (sufficient), complete (complete), detailed (quite detailed), great fairly deal of (many), detailed (detailed), limited (limited), wide (wide), great (great, large), a piece of (part), in- depth (deep), lack of (lack), some (some), useful (useful), up to date (modern), background (underlying), formal (formal), precise (exact, definite), active (active), passive (passive), new (new), necessary (necessary), present (present), previous (previous), general (general), prior (previous), special (special), elementary (elementary, initial), paramount (primary), simple (simple), implicit (implied), explicit (fully stated, leaving no doubt, precise, definite), factual (actual, acting, based on facts), genuine (genuine), ordinary (ordinary), useless (useless), varied (varied), reasonable (reasonable) knowledge [BE], etc.

According to the D21 sememe, an emotional assessment can be expressed available body of knowledge: a positive assessment: expert (experienced, skillful), remarkable (wonderful), good (good), true (true, truthful), right (correct), powerful

(powerful), to draw confidence from (get confidence from); negative assessment: to quiver with (tremble, tremble from), to make somebody reckless (to make someone reckless, reckless, careless), distressing knowledge [BE], etc.

The D21 sememe is updated in phrases that mean operating with existing knowledge: appearance: to acquire (acquire, receive), to accumulate (accumulate), to gain (receive, acquire), to absorb (absorb), to assimilate (assimilate), to soak up (absorb) [CD, 1990,139], to bring new (bring new), to provide (provide), acquisition of (acquisition), to get (receive) knowledge [BE], etc.; presence, retention: to cultivate (accumulate, increase), to demonstrate (demonstrate), to display (show, discover), to show (show), to parade (put on display), to flaunt (important), to brush up (refresh) [CD, 1990,139], to expand (expand), to reinforce (strengthen, reinforce), to refine (improve quality, go into subtleties), to

formalize (formalize), to have (have), to obtain (acquire), growth of (growth), to develop (develop), to test (check), to reveal (discover, open, issue), to be dependant upon (depend on), to increase (increase), to improve (improve), pursuit of (pursuit), to piece together fragments of knowledge (join fragments together), fountain of (fountain), to add to (add to), to exploit (exploit), to apply (apply, apply, use), to extend (expand), to use (use), to recall (remember), to be full of (to be complete), appetite for knowledge remains (appetite to knowledge remains), to systematize (systematize) knowledge [BE], etc.; transfer: to communicate (transfer), to disseminate (distribute), to impart (transfer, give) [CD, 1990,139], to exchange (exchange), to share (share) knowledge [BE], etc.

These phrases describe the content of knowledge and are not included in the LSP of mental states.

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